

CROSSTRACK DYNAMICS OF A LONG CABLE TOWED IN THE OCEAN

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ABSTRACT

This paper documents a study of the horizontal motion of the downstream end of a towed cable when the motion of the towing vessel is known. The dynamic position of the downstream end of the cable is a consequence of the random crosstrack meandering of the towing vessel as it imperfectly maintains a constant course. The specific purpose of the study was to supply a method to predict the horizontal motion. Other contributors to cable dynamics, such as ocean current, are not addressed.

A linear theory for the transverse motion of a cable being towed without purposeful maneuvers was developed. A cable experiment was then performed at sea to verify the linear theory and to establish parameters that would apply operationally in the sea environment. Specifically, the linear transfer function relating the transverse horizontal motion of the upstream and downstream ends of a long steel cable was calculated and measured.

INTRODUCTION

Ocean engineers frequently tow an instrumentation package at the end of a long cable. It is important in such a case to know the position of the instrumentation package during the period in which the towing vessel is attempting to maintain a constant course. The degree of precision needed depends on the task itself. This precision can vary from tens of meters in an oceanographic application to tens of centimeters for some acoustic applications. This paper documents the findings of a study to understand the transverse dynamics of the cable, and to make available a real-time at-sea position predicting capability.

In the past, approximate numerical schemes have been used to simulate the dynamic conditions of interest. Such studies have not been physically enlightening. The calculations require significant computer

capability and are long and costly. Currently there is little hope that such computational power can be made available at sea. Our approach, in this paper, was different; we sought explicit solutions of approximate partial differential equations describing the cable dynamics. The result of this approach has been an improved understanding of the physical processes involved, as well as a simple analytical description of the dynamics.

This paper consists of three parts. First, a physical description of the horizontal transverse dynamics of a neutrally buoyant case is discussed. Second, the neutrally buoyant case is modified to account for the more typical situation of a negatively buoyant cable. This is done without having to solve the complex three-dimensional problem. Finally, the analytical results are compared with the results of an experiment designed to evaluate the theory.

ANALYTICAL PROBLEM

Let us begin by describing the two-dimensional cable problem illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Two-Dimensional Problem

The tow vessel and cable are in a coordinate system such that the "X" axis is the mean course of the vessel, and the "Y" axis always contains the tow point. This requires the coordinate system to translate with the vessel. That is, the tow point is always on the X=0 boundary. Fluid flows from left to right at a velocity U, and the tow point and cable have transverse motions in the Y direction with a typical amplitude, a. The track of the tow vessel exhibits characteristic lengths, λ , and the array is L long. We define an along-track wave number in the X direction that is related to the frequency of the vertical oscillations of the tow point by the dispersion relation shown. The principal assumption of the problem is that the wave number-amplitude product is a small number. This means that we restrict ourselves to the situation in which the towing vessel is attempting to proceed on a straight course, but exhibits small crosstrack meandering.

In the mid 1960's, Paidoussis, a Canadian, developed a linear momentum equation describing the transverse dynamics of the two-dimensional problem (Figure 2). While we do not have the time here to discuss the mathematics, I would like to quickly bring to your attention the forces involved in the problem. In Figure 2, those forces are, from left to right, the cable and fluid inertial forces, the cable bending stiffness, the "string-like" tension stiffness caused by the longitudinal hydrodynamic drag, and, finally, a velocity damping term supplied by the normal hydrodynamic drag. Paidoussis argued that the normal hydrodynamic drag would be directly proportional to fluid velocity at small fluid-cable angles. Recently, Paul Rispin at the Naval Ship Research and Development Center performed experiments that verified the "small angle" form used by Paidoussis. Specifically the Paidoussis form applies for cable-fluid angles less than 2.5 to 3 degrees.

Typical power series and numerical integration techniques to solve the Paidoussis equation have not been very illuminating and have resulted in numerically complex expressions. In order to simplify the numerical expressions and gain a physical understanding of the process, the equations have been solved using approximate techniques. These approximations exploit the fact that the balance between various physical forces changes quite significantly for different forced vibration frequencies. That is, at low frequencies the dominant balance of terms is quite different than it is at high frequencies. Thus we have broken the solution up into two parts and applied singular perturbation and WKB-type techniques to solving the governing equation in each frequency region.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{INERTIAL FORCES} \\
 \text{OF} \\
 \text{CYLINDER} \quad \text{FLUID MASS} \\
 m \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} + M \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right)^2 y + EI \frac{\partial^4 y}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} c_T \frac{M}{D} U^2 (L-x) \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right\} \\
 \text{DAMPING TERM} \\
 \text{DUE TO TRANSVERSE DRAG} \\
 + \frac{1}{2} c_N \frac{MU}{D} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right) y = 0
 \end{array}$$

Where:

- m** is cylinder linear mass
- M** is fluid linear mass
- D** is cylinder diameter
- E** is cylinder elastic modulus
- I** is cylinder radius of gyration
- c_T** is longitudinal drag coefficient
- c_N** is transverse drag coefficient

Figure 2. Paidoussis Equation

In Figure 3, the results of the approximate solutions are summarized by showing the transfer function between the tow-point and any point on the cable. This transfer function viewpoint is possible since the governing differential equation is a linear one.

It is useful analytically and experimentally to specify the dynamics of the cable in terms of a transfer function from the tow vessel to any point on the cable. In Figure 3 the complex transfer function is shown as a function of a non-dimensional frequency along the common abscissa. The ordinate in the upper figure is the magnitude of the complex transfer function expressed in decibels. The ordinate of the lower graph is the phase velocity responsible for the phase shift associated with the transfer function.

From Figure 3 we can summarize the response of the physical system to a forced vibration at the towpoint. Over a range of real excitation frequencies, the cable responds in three distinct manners. At low frequencies the inertial and curvature forces are small and the response of the cable is controlled by hydrodynamic forces. The result is that deformations, put into the cable by the towing vessel, convect downstream relatively unattenuated at the tow speed. This physically explains an often repeated at-sea observation when a flexible body is towed behind a ship: if the vessel puts a knuckle into the cable, that knuckle convects along the cable at the tow speed. In other words, the vessel appears to bore a hole in the water and the cable simply follows through that hole. This has sometimes been referred to as the "water pulley" effect.

Note that the deformation convects as opposed to propagates. As the frequency of the forced vibration increases, inertial forces and tension stiffness of the cable become important and wave systems typical of string waves are produced. These waves always have a phase velocity which is greater than the tow speed and which slow up as one proceeds aft. This slowing up is a consequence of the diminishing tension. Finally, as the frequency becomes large and the wave lengths become small, the response of the cable is dominated by the flexural rigidity of the cable and beam-type waves are produced. Figure 3 shows these three regions smoothly connected. In the string region the velocity damping significantly attenuates the vibration. However, as you get to the beam region, flexural stiffness of the cable itself is so stiff that fluid damping forces are negligible and the cable begins to act like a beam situated in a vacuum. The beam region is not of practical interest to our stated problem because the vessel contributes little energy at such high frequencies. For our purposes, we may consider the cable to act like a dispersive low-pass filter.

Figure 3. Complex Transfer Function

Let us now look to see what effect, if any, the vertical depression angle of the cable has on horizontal transverse forces.

In Figure 4, a cable is being towed in the negative Y direction. With respect to the coordinate system in the illustration, the fluid moves in the positive Y direction.

Figure 4. Cable Depression Angle Effects

We are interested in forces in the X direction, the transverse direction of the cable.

In Figure 4, the cable has a depression angle φ and a horizontal attack angle θ. Until now we have only considered the angle θ. Some rather straight forward but tedious arithmetic allows us to write the expression for the normal drag force vector. The transverse or X component is dependent upon both θ and φ. For example, if θ were zero, the normal force would have no transverse component. If, however, the cable assumes a horizontal angle θ, then a horizontal transverse component exists which, as we see from the expression in the figure, is a function of both θ and φ. Thus we see that there is an interaction of the orthogonal vertical and horizontal forces. This phenomenon is frequently encountered. For example, anyone in a small car recognizes that when he encounters a cross flow, the amount of side force is dependent on how fast he is going. That is, the faster he goes, the larger the drag force vector is that is available to be tilted into the transverse direction. This is what is shown in the illustration. The vertical angle establishes a large drag force as a consequence of the depression angle. The horizontal angle then establishes a transverse flow. The transverse flow tilts the force vector into the horizontal direction. The physical consequence is that there is an amplification of the horizontal force as a consequence of the vertical depression angle. Analytically, we can conveniently incorporate this interaction by amplifying the normal coefficient of drag to account for the phenomenon.

Let us summarize our analytical work as follows: Approximate solutions were found which describe the transverse dynamics of a long flexible cable in axial flow. The solution to this two-dimensional problem was modified to account for the effect of a steady cable depression angle by increasing the normal drag coefficient. Finally, a transfer function was used to describe the dynamics.

EXPERIMENT

To verify the theory, we performed an experiment. Figure 5 illustrates the experimental configuration.

Figure 5. Experimental Configuration

A 16-mm diameter steel cable was towed from a surface vessel. The ship was maneuvered to force sinusoidal horizontal transverse motion at the upstream end of the cable. During each run, the cable was towed through a number of cycles. Each run was defined by a set of three parameters combined in a factorial type experiment. The variables were ship's speed, cable length, and oscillation frequency. Transverse motion of both ends of the cable was carefully measured by acoustically tracking pingers attached to the ship and the cable at the point to be measured. The ship maneuvers simulated a sinusoidal upstream boundary condition; the response of the system to the stimulation was measured by the track of the pinger at the other end of the cable. A neutrally buoyant cylinder supplied tension to the end of the cable.

The objective of the data analysis was to compare the experimental and theoretical results. An exact contrast was possible through comparison of calculated and measured values of the complex transfer function between the two pingers. Experimentally the transfer function was determined by calculating the Fourier transform of the time series of the crosstrack displacement for both pingers. Transfer function magnitude and phase speed were then determined from the ratio of the transforms.

The results of the experiment are shown in Figure 6 which illustrates the transfer function between the ship and the end of the cable.

The ordinate of the upper graph in Figure 6 is the magnitude of the transfer function, and the ordinate of the lower graph is the nondimensional phase velocity. The large dots in the figure are the measured values of the transfer function. The solid lines are theoretical curves resulting from the theory. All the parameters used in the calculations are well known from previous experience except for the normal drag coefficient. The value used for this coefficient was determined from an experiment performed by Dr. Rispin for cables towed at angles less than 2.5 degrees. That value was then increased to account for cable depression and attack angles encountered in the experiment. The amplification which best fits the data was a factor of 2-1/2. First, note the curve marked "Rispin normal drag coefficient modified for cylinder depression angle."

Figure 6. Theory-Experiment Comparison

These are the curves which best fit both the phase and magnitude of the transfer function for a single value of C_n . In order to better fit the complex transfer function, it was necessary to choose different values of C_n for the two curves.

RESULTS

The result of the comparison between theory and practice is that while we are confident that we have modeled the dominant physical forces, the absence of a

single value of the normal drag coefficient that best fits both the amplitude and phase of the measured transfer function, illustrates that the two-dimensional linear model is imperfect. A better fit to the theory would probably be possible with a more rigorous handling of the three-dimensional dynamics and the hydrodynamic normal drag term. However, with the technique shown, we have been able to account for better than 90 percent of the motion observed at the end of the cable. To improve on this record would require a significant analytical effort.